

REMEDIATION OF CHROMIUM WITH LOW COST ADSORBENTS

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ABSTRACT

Hexavalent Cr (VI) ion is well recognized as an element of environmental and public health concern Chromium is an essential element that is required in small amounts for carbohydrate metabolism, but becomes toxic at higher concentrations. Nowadays, water pollution is increasing rapidly, due to urbanization, population growth, and quick industrialization discharge a huge amount of potentially toxic metals and untreated waste into surface and groundwater The waste released from tanneries process consumed 60–70% of total chromium, whereas, the rest of 30–40% remains unconsumed. This unconsumed chromium goes away with the industrial pollution due to the tanning process with Cr-salt and consequently, large quantities of Cr are being discharged by polluting surface waters, soil, air, land, and groundwater

Activated carbons are used in full scale operations in developed countries, however their use is not suitable for developing countries due to their high manufacturing cost . Most water treatment technologies suitable for the developed countries are expensive for towns and small industries of the developing countries because of limitation of funds and lack of skilled man power .There is a increasing search for low cost adsorbent There is a increasing search for low cost adsorbent material made from locally available waste material and plant substrata Remediation of chromium with low cost adsorbents offers a cheap and sludge free method has been highlighted in this paper.

INTRODUCTION

Chromium is an essential element that is required in small amounts for carbohydrate metabolism, but becomes toxic at higher concentrations. The most bioavailable and therefore most toxic form of chromium is the hexavalent Cr (VI) ion.

Nowadays, water pollution is increasing rapidly, due to urbanization, population growth, and quick industrialization, at an increasing degree, frequently discharge a huge amount of potentially toxic chromium metals and untreated waste into surface and groundwater. The waste released from tanneries process consumed 60–70% of total chromium, whereas, the rest of 30–40% remains unconsumed. This unconsumed chromium goes away with the industrial pollution due to the tanning process with Cr-salt and consequently, large quantities of Cr are being discharged by polluting surface waters, soil, air, land, and groundwater[Xuan Hoa Vu 2019]

Percolation of chromium in the groundwater of industrial areas of india . [Table 1] [Poonam Tyagi et al 1999]

AREA	mg/L	INDUSTRY
Rourkela Bihar	0- 0.01	steel plant
Cochin ,Kerala	0.008- 0.019	Tanneries
Jharia Bihar	0.01- 0.09	Ore -mining
Himachal Pradesh	0.001- 0.019	Ore -mining
Harayana		Bi cycles
Punjab		wollen garments

Hexavalent chromium is a group “A” human carcinogen because of its mutagenic and carcinogenic properties also in the priority list of hazardous substances since it affects both; human and aquatic life. It has been reported that excessive intake of hexavalent chromium by plants severely affects the mitotic process and reduce seed germination in extensively cultivated pulse crops [Sarkar B., 2002] Trace amounts of Cr is considered essential for normal metabolic processes (metallo-enzymes), however intakes at higher levels have been found toxic mainly kidneys and liver Hepato and nephrotoxic effects have been reported in rats [Meenakshi 1989].

Cr is highly toxic to fish and other aquatic life ,causes changes in oxygen uptake and blood parameters in the fish Sarotherodon mossambicus (Peters) [Pamila.D 1991] Hexavalent form of Chromium is more toxic than trivalent form , Cr (VI) causes bronchial cancer in man .The maximum permissible limit of Cr in drinking water ,as recommended by WHO is 0.05 mg/l Chromium has been widely used in industry for many years with the toxicity of Cr (VI) being well recognized as a health related problem .

The industrial town of Kanpur in Uttar Pradesh has a many cotton textiles ,chrome leather tanning , chemical manufacturing industries . A survey was conducted and found that in comparison to other industrial areas of India the ground water of this area contains a very high concentration Cr (VI) [Figure 1.] With regard to the study zone of Rakhmandi in Kanpur is of particular significance which is mainly due to subsurface disposal of chromium-rich sludge ,indiscriminately disposed (along with municipal garbage) by units manufacturing basic chrome sulphate ,the chromium leachates acidic in nature imparts a moderately yellow hue and supports leaching of cationic sulphates . More than 80% of tanneries in India and other asian countries adopt chrome tanning practiceIn traditional chrome tanning practice only 50-60% of the chromium applied is taken up by leather and the balance is discharged as waste.Indian tanneries numbering more than 3,000 use annually 45 ,000 metric tons of basic chromium sulphate [BCS] out of this quantity 20,000 tons of chromium salt is discharged in wastewater streams. These discharges cause pollution, waste costly chemicals , and complicate effluent treatment particularly anaerobic biological treatment and disposal of chromium containing sludge The study zone of Jajmau housing a cluster of tanneries presents altogether a contrasting scenario on account of its situation being hydrodynamically upstream of the river , the basic ascribable reason is the possible wash out of the pollutants percolating through the ground and ultimately reaching the river in the proximity [GWQS/8/1996-97]

FIGURE 1 CHROMIUM IN GROUNDWATER OF INDUSTRIAL AREAS OF KANPUR CITY ,UTTAR PRADESH, INDIA

EXISTING METHODS FOR Cr(VI) REMOVAL

The author wishes to draw attention toward the fact that various technologies are available for removing Cr (VI), including reduction and precipitation, ion-exchange ,precipitation of chromate with barium or lead, ion-flotation , electro dialysis , liquid– liquid extraction and reverse osmosis ,the process of adsorption has a an edge over other methods ,due to its simplicity and sludge free clean operation. The most widely used method is to first detoxify Cr (VI) by reducing to the Cr (III) form , which is about 100 times less toxic . This can be accomplished with reducing agents such as SO₂ , ferrous-sulphate , sodium bisulphite or other sulphite . Then precipitation of chromium is induced by the addition of a base . A major problem with this type of treatment is the disposal of precipitated chromium hydroxide . Metal hydroxides tend to be highly hydrated and voluminous stable colloids containing as much as 80 % water by volume due to the slower replacment of coordinate water for hydroxide ions

.Ion-exchange treatment does not present a sludge disposal problem and has the advantage of reclaimation of Cr (VI) . However , Ion-exchange treatment does have disadvantages of being expensive ,being poorly selective for chromate over foreign anions and of having a critical flow rate necessary for efficient removal

Biological removal of toxic Cr was tried using an Enterobactor cloaca strain that reduces under anaerobic conditions . [Komori 1990] The bacteria Enterobactor cloaca removes toxic Cr (VI) by reducing it to Cr (III) , this trivalent Cr forms Cr(OH)₃ which can be separated using negatively charged materials . This method may also create sludge problems .

Adsorption at solid solution interfaces is an important means of controlling the extent of pollution due to metallic species of industrial effluents . Adsorptive capacity is the most

important property of the adsorbent, because it determines how much waste water can be treated per unit of adsorbent. Adsorptive capacity determines both the direct operating cost of the treatment and sizing of equipment. The factors which influence adsorption are molecular structure or nature of adsorbate, temperature and the presence of the other adsorbates. molecular structure or nature of adsorbate are responsible for providing the adsorbent, a receptive surface for adsorption. The micropores present allow easy access of fluids into the interior of the sorbent. In many applications, the preliminary evaluation programme takes the form of a simple study where the capacities are determined by batch technique in the laboratory. Activated carbons are widely used as adsorbents for purification of aqueous solutions of chromium [Jung .I.Kim 1997] as adsorption has an edge over other methods, due to its simplicity and sludge free clean operation. Activated carbons are used in full scale operations in developed countries, however their use is not suitable for developing countries due to their high manufacturing cost. Most water treatment technologies suitable for the developed countries are expensive for towns and small industries of the developing countries because of limitation of funds and lack of skilled man power. There is an increasing search for low cost adsorbent material made from locally available waste material and plant substrata. The Table 2 lists some of low cost adsorbents which have been earlier reported. Alternative low cost method is removal of Cr(VI) from tannery effluent using waterweeds [P.Singaram, 1994], three water weeds *Eichhornia crassipes*, *Lemna pseudo water hyacinth* and *Salvinia natans* were allowed to grow in the tannery effluents from Tanneries at Ambur Dist, Tamil Nadu. and were able to remove Cr(VI) from the water

TABLE 2 LOW COST ADSORBENTS FOR Cr(VI) REMOVAL FROM WATER

ADSORBENTS	REFERENCE
Baggase	M.Rao 1999
Baggase carbon	GM Shantha 1993
Bituminous coal	Narayan, N 1989
Brick kiln ash	AK Rai 1999
Fly ash	Haribabu 1992
Fly ash-china clay	K K Pandey 1984
Fly ash –Wollasonite	K K Pandey 1984
Groundnut husk carbon	K.Peraswamy 1991
Human hair	TC Tani 1985
Haematite	D B Singh 1994
Iron coated sand	R P Bailey 1992
Leaf powders	M. Vasanthy 1993
<i>Magnifera indica</i> leaves	D K Singh 1993
Peat Moss	B Coupal 1996
<i>Pinus slyvestris</i> bark	M M Alves 1993
Rice straw	Nandita Deo 1992
Rice husk ash	T K Bansal 1992
Rice husk carbon	K Srinivasan 1988
Sawdust	DK Singh 1990
Tea leaves carbon	Jyotsna . Lal 1992
Tamarind hull	Verma Chakraborty 2006
Sugar industrial waste	Fahim 2006
Treated rice straw	KS Sai Prasad 2015
Tannery solid waste	Rahaman 2016

Coffe husk	Dessalew Berihun 2017
Spent tea leaves	Nur-E-Alam 2018
Snail shell	Xuan Hoa 2019
Carbonized chat stem	Yogezu 2021
Mango Jackfruit seeds	Deendayal 2021

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

Reagents and Methods : Solutions of Cr (VI) were prepared in tapwater using $K_2Cr_2O_7$ (BDH,India) pH was adjusted with HCl .Presence of Cr (VI) in the effluent was determined by Diphenyl Carbazide All the reagents used were analytical grade .

Locally available sawdust was sieved (60-100 mesh) was treated with water to remove the impurities ,then the water was filtered off using cloth bag .

\Waste tea leaves (TL)were treated hot dimineralised water ,dried at 100 oC . A pseudo activated carbon was prepared by reacting 10 gm TL/10ml H_2SO_4 The carbonised material was washed with DMW and dried at 100 oC , sieved (60-100 mesh) gave the Adsorbent waste tealeaves carbon .

Rice straw was procured from the fodder of the local market cut 1cm long size ,soaked in water overnight ,washed free of colored impurities and dried. Sieved (60-100 mesh)

Adsorption Capacity by column and batch technique

Breakthrough capacity of Cr (VI) was determined by passing Cr (VI) solution through a glass column (i.d.1.25cm) packed with 5gm adsorbent on a glasswool support The flow rate was maintained at 125 ml/h .Batch studies were carried out in glass stoppered conical flasks containing 100ml solution with different dosage and contact time in a mechanical shaker.

FIGURE 5 CHROMIUM (VI) REMOVAL BY TEALEAVES CARBON

FIGURE 3 CHROMIUM (VI) REMOVAL BY SAWDUST

FIGURE 4 CHROMIUM(VI) REMOVAL BY RICE STRAW

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Some low cost adsorbents selective for Cr(VI) have been tested in the laboratory by batch and column technique pH, concentration and flow rate on break-through capacity have been investigated. The author compared some adsorbents which are available through out the year Human Hair was a poor adsorbent at pH range 1-5 removed 1.1mg Cr/gm [Tan.T.C 1985] Similarly Brick kiln ash showed only 50% removal as compared to Fly ash at pH 1.3 from chromeplating wastewater as shown in Figure 2 [Rai. AK 1999] Bituminous coal at pH 2 removed 2.5mg/gm [Narayan.N.1989] Adsorbent made from a mixture Fly ash – Chinaclay showed 100% removal at pH 2 from solution 4.3mg Cr(VI)/L [Pandey .K.K 1984] Columns packed with Sawdust a natural inexpensive material, available everywhere can be utilized as low cost adsorbent for the removal of CrVI from aqueous solution, the adsorption capacity was determined as 97.5 mg/5gm or 19.5mg/gm at pH~2 Break through capacity as a function of pH is plotted in Figure 3 Rice straw a inexpensive material can be utilized as low cost adsorbent for the removal of CrVI from aqueous solution [Figure 4], the adsorption capacity was determined 25mg Cr/gm Baggase is reported to remove 80.80% at pH 6-7 from solution 3.5gm Cr(VI)/L [Rao.M 1999] Tea leaves carbon [TLC] can play an important role in treatment processes of metal bearing industrial effluents, a cheap carbonaceous adsorbent made from waste tea leaves Break through capacity 39.3mg/gm. In Figure 5, Cr(VI) removal as as function of pH and carbon dosage can be seen. The amount of TLC required for 100% Cr(VI) removal 433mgCr(VI)/L carbon dosage 1200mg/L at pH 1.5 –2.0. Author compares TLC to Groundnut husk carbon GHC It can be seen that, Activated Groundnut husk carbon at pH range 0.5-1.7 showed 100% removal from 10mg Cr(VI)/L solution, carbon dosage 2400mg/L in Figure 6 [Periswamy .K 1991] Presence of holocellulose and lignin on sawdust and rice straw can be explained for removal of CrVI from aqueous solution Sigworth and Smith 1972 have proposed the possibility of heavy metal precipitation on the carbon surface by nucleation as one of the pathways for heavy metal removal by activated carbon

CONCLUSION

Rice straw, Baggase and Sawdust are natural inexpensive materials, which are easily available and do not require chemical pretreatment. Exhibit exceptionally high degree of Cr(VI) adsorption, thus can be utilized for treatment of industrial waste effluents containing Cr(VI). On the other hand Tea leaves carbon TLC and Groundnut husk carbon GHC are excellent cheap carbonaceous adsorbents showing high degree of Cr(VI) adsorption. These adsorbents can easily prepared in any laboratory of a tannery, chrome plating or paint industry. These adsorbents offer a good alternative to expensive activated carbons and other water treatment technologies. These adsorbents can be ashed to recover the adsorbed Cr, a possible solution to the disposal of Cr containing sludge which is classified as hazardous. This paper has been limited to a study of adsorption capacities at different pH for some low cost asorbents. There is a need to describe the mechanisms responsible for removal of Cr(VI) from aqueous solution by these low cost asorbents, Cr(VI) adsorption and reduction to Cr(III) by these Adsorbents, using Adsorption isotherms.

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